

The problem of formation of moral values in the process of teaching mathematics

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The article discusses the problem of formation of moral values in the process of teaching mathematics. It reveals the fact that this process has a great potential for formation of both positive and negative moral values. We focus on the basic universal moral values - kindness, respect, love, dignity, duty, justice, tolerance, the purpose of life, happiness. We consider the problem of formation of moral values within the general approach to the problem and in the context of informatization of mathematical education. We suggest specific ways to prevent the formation of negative values and to encourage the formation of positive moral ones in the process of teaching mathematics. We find value-orientation teaching of mathematics as an approach to reach the goal.

Introduction

The formation of moral values is one of the main tasks of education. The possibilities of humanitarian school subjects in the formation of moral values of students are undoubtedly great. Literature and history may address to works depicting excellent artistic images or historical figures with excellent moral qualities of heroism, love or kindness, while the educational material of mathematics does not provide such opportunities. Nevertheless, the process of teaching mathematics also has a great potential for the formation of both positive and negative moral values (Mikaelian, 2011, 2015a, 2017; Yenokyan, 2019b).

Despite the fact that quite a lot of attention has been recently paid to the relationship between mathematics and ethics (Ernest, 2016, 2018; François, 2018; Mendick, 2006), the problem of formation of moral values in the process of teaching mathematics seems to be left out of this framework. Our works in this direction are published in Armenian and Russian (some of them are included to the list of references) and they are not available to a wide range of specialists. This publication will fill the gap. Due to space constraints, our wordings is shorter than we feel like, so we do not dwell on the problems of formation of the moral values of respect, justice, freedom, love, etc. It would also be interesting to demonstrate a practical presentation of value-orientated learning in the process of teaching mathematics, which is not carried out for the same reason.

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We have been guided by the following principles in presenting the results of our research on the forming of moral values through the process of teaching mathematics.

a) First of all, designate good as a basic moral value, the possibility of forming good and prevent evil in the process of teaching mathematics and their connection with other moral values. This topic has been extensively studied by various authors. b) Present the moral values formed in the process of teaching mathematics, interesting for the MES and perhaps not previously studied by other authors. From this perspective, we examined the moral values of duty and virtue. In addition, in the case of duty, we were guided only by Kant's ideas about this moral category, and we considered the value of virtue in the context of historical development, taking into account the philosophical approaches of different times. c) Present the relationship and dependence on worldview and various philosophical ideas that the formation of moral values in the process of teaching mathematics has. The paragraph on the meaning of life and happiness in our work is presented with this approach. d) To present the problem of formation of moral values in the context of modern approaches of mathematical education: humanization and informatization.

Good and evil in the process of teaching mathematics

Good and evil are the most important moral values. Although there are different opinions about good and evil in the nature of a person (Kant, 1965; Mikaelian, 2011), there is a prevailing idea of their formation through education in all approaches. The process of teaching mathematics occupies a special place in the formation of the values of good and evil of students.

Firstly, good is a boon, that is, beneficial. Mathematics education is a boon. It is a boon as a component of education; a boon in terms of its applied purpose, in terms of the role it plays in the functions of formation and development of intelligence, in the mental processes of students. However, experience shows that the vast majority of students do not take advantage of this boon. Moreover, a mathematical lesson for them becomes a repulsive, unpleasant environment or evil (Ernest, 2018; Mikaelian, 2011). In the process of teaching mathematics, it is difficult to carry out the formation of such a sign that characterizes good as tolerance. In their works Mikaelian (2015a) and Yenokyan (2016) examine the psychological and moral consequences of a teacher's intolerance for a student's mistake, their delay in response and other actions and ways to avoid them.

As a rule, students with high academic performance are given manifestation of kindness on the part of the teacher, whereas it is the weak students who need this but do not receive it. Even one encouraging word by the teacher while solving a simple exercise can draw such a student into the learning process. The teacher's behaviour should not contain such signs of evil as rancour, revenge, suppression of someone else's will, coercion, ill will, pressure, hatred or revenge (Mikaelian, 2015a). Mikaelian (2011) also discusses the formation of such qualities inherent in good as benevolence, respect, compassion, lack of rancour and revenge. Yenokyan (2019a) discusses the issue of preventing the qualities inherent in evil in the process of teaching mathematics.

The moral duty in the process of teaching mathematics

Duty is the ability to recognize one's own moral responsibility. The role of education is great in the awareness, formation and implementation of duty. Mathematics also has necessary educational potential in this direction, the identification of which was carried out in Mikaelian (2011) where we consider a person's duty in relation to themselves and others. Kant (1965) identifies three types of duty in relation to themselves in which a person acts as a living being, a spiritual being or a moral being.

The duty of a person towards oneself, as a living being, primarily implies the obligation to maintain existence for which they try to satisfy their vital needs. The process of teaching mathematics pushes a person to intellectual actions and helps to strengthen willpower, properties that contribute to the satisfaction of life's needs. At the same time, long-term mental work, work with an imaginary world, which is inherent in those engaged in mathematics, is aimed at keeping a person from communicating with nature and people, that is, from the natural essence of a person. That can lead to poor health and contradicts the duty of attitude towards oneself as a living being. Duty to oneself, as a living being, also implies the preservation of the human species, for which a person creates a family, gives birth to children, takes care of them and raises them. Presumably, the process of teaching mathematics, while increasing the intellectual abilities of a person, does not contribute to the fulfilment of this duty. It does not contribute to the realization of communication with people, which is also a duty in relation to oneself as a living being.

According to Kant (1980) a person's duty towards oneself as a spiritual being is the development of spiritual, mental and physical forces. Among the spiritual values, Kant first notes mathematics. However, mathematics not only constitutes the most important part of the human spiritual world, but also makes a significant contribution to the development of other essential components of the human spiritual world - science and technology, acts as an indispensable tool for the formation of various branches of art, as an important means of forming beauty in them. Mathematical education plays an important role in the formation and development of thinking, imagination, memory, attention, will and other mental processes, and these in turn contribute to the development of spiritual forces (Mikaelian, 2015b, 2019, 2020; Ernest, 2020; Francois, 2019).

Mikaelian, (2011) considers the issue of manifestations of a person's moral duty towards oneself in the process of teaching mathematics- moral self-knowledge as the first dictate of duty to oneself and conscience as the ability to assess one's own activities, to see oneself as an inner judge. It also examines the relationship between the process of teaching mathematics with falsehood, servility, avarice - vices that lead to a violation of duty towards oneself as a moral being. In relation to the third, mathematics has different roles. In everyday matters it leads to stinginess; in the intellectual sphere it leads to formation of extravagance and in the professional sphere it leads to the formation of generosity.

Kant distinguishes between two types of duty in relation to others- love and respect. Mikaelian (2011) discusses the manifestation of love and respect in the processes of teaching

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mathematics. The author mainly shows that the competitive nature of mathematical activity can hinder the formation of a common duty of love in relation to another – philanthropy (Mikaelian, 2018a). The process of teaching mathematics has many opportunities for the manifestation of charity, gratitude and compassion as debts of love towards others. In this process may also appear the vices of ingratitude, envy and malice in the two-sided subjective teacher–student or student–student relations. These vices are contrary to the duty of love. A teacher has to be skilful to lead the process in the necessary direction.

Mikaelian (2011) considers the problem of the manifestation of a duty of respect towards others in the process of teaching mathematics in two-way subjective relations of teacher–student and student–student. It discusses the possibilities of manifestation in this process of arrogance, ridicule and slander, vices contradicting the duty of respect towards others. We need to be especially careful about the duty of respect. Indeed, while neglect of the duty of love does not harm anyone, disregard of the duty of respect insults one’s dignity.

Feeling of respect is closely related to that of love. Just as in the physical world, bodies are in harmony due to the balance of the forces of attraction and repulsion, harmony is carried out using the balance of the forces of attraction and repulsion and moral harmony between people is the result of the balance of these forces of attraction and repulsion - love and respect (Kant,1980). In the process of teaching mathematics, moral harmony between the student and the teacher of mathematics, based on mutual love and respect, is realized only with students with good academic performance (Mikaelian, 2011).

Virtue and vice in the process of teaching maths

The first doctrine of virtue was developed by *Aristotle* (Aristotle, 1983). He viewed virtue as a golden mean between two extreme vices - excess and lack. Thus, courage is something between madness and cowardice; generosity in relation to material goods is something between extravagance and stinginess; truthfulness is something between of boasting and hypocrisy, wit is something between buffoonery and rudeness. Friendliness is something between quarrelsomeness and quarrelsomeness, bashfulness is something between shamelessness and timidity, etc. Mikaelian (2011) considers the possibilities of applying these approaches of Aristotle in the process of teaching mathematics. It is shown that they can enable the mathematics teacher to keep the learning process from unnecessary extremes or the danger of the formation of vices. There are drawings that characterize the manifestations of Aristotelian virtues in the process of teaching mathematics, the accuracy of which has been experimentally confirmed. For example, Figure 1 is a representation of the formation of the Aristotelian concept of the virtue of courage. The drawing conventionally depicts areas of cowardice, courage and madness. The marked layer shows to which of these areas math education pushes the student. We see that mathematics education is inherent in keeping a person from madness, not pushing for courage and generating a sense towards of fear of danger.

Figure 1: Courage and mathematics

The next group of virtues comprises the “radical” virtues of ancient Greece: moderation, courage, wisdom and justice. Mikaelian (2011) discusses the influence of mathematical education on the process of formation of these moral qualities in students. Mikaelian (2011) also discusses the role of mathematics education in the formation of the basic theological virtues of hope, faith and love. For the formation of all these virtues, as well as the corresponding vices, mathematics has a great educational potential, the manifestation and prevention of which depends on the activities of the teacher.

Let us turn to *Solov’ev’s* understanding of virtue and the role of mathematical education in its formation. According to Solovyov (2012) three qualities shame, compassion and cowardice lie in the basis of virtues. In the process of teaching mathematics, manifestations of Solov’ev’s understanding of shame and cowardice are often encountered, while compassion is manifested in exceptional cases.

B. Franklin (Franklin, 1956) also turns to virtues. He finds that the virtue of human activity has to be measured by its usefulness for achieving success and identifies a number of virtues, three of which are considered the main ones. There are hard work, accurate fulfilment of monetary obligations and frugality. In the formation of all these virtues, mathematics education plays a significant positive role (Mikaelian, 2011).

Meaning, purpose of life, happiness and the process of teaching mathematics.

The meaning of life is one of the highest moral values, which is related to the determination of the ultimate goal of existence, the purpose of humanity as a biological species, as individuals. The meaning of life is one of the main worldview concepts that are of great importance for the formation of the spiritual and moral appearance of a person. Can the process of teaching mathematics contribute to the formation of this moral value? The answer to the question depends on our approaches to this concept: what do we consider the meaning of life? Different philosophical directions answer this question in different ways.

If we proceed from the ideas of *hedonism*, then the meaning of life is limited to pleasure. In (Mikaelian, 2015b) it is shown that pleasure can arise both from the identification of the internal structure of mathematical material, and from the use of mathematics in solving problems that have appeared in different academic subjects. In both cases, pleasure is associated with beauty. In the first case, we are dealing with signs of mathematical beauty in the form of intellectual search, finding, and discovery, and in the second case with signs of applicability (Mikaelian, 2019).

Utilitarianism is premised on the fact that the meaning of life involves obtaining benefits (a variant of egoism) or giving benefits (a variant of altruism). Mikaelian (2018a) shows that the process of teaching mathematics is mainly selfish. It is aimed at obtaining benefits. In

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relation to others or by a pro-social nature, mathematical activity is not altruistic, but sadistic. Consequently, within the framework of general education, it mainly leads to competition. In addition, the benefits of mathematics education are obvious from the point of view of spiritual development and the formation of the students' worldview, the achievement of professional success in the future, and so on (Ernest, 2020; Mikaelian, 2020a).

Let us turn to the problem in detail from the standpoint of *eudemonism* where the meaning of life is limited to happiness. There are various moral approaches to happiness that do not satisfy the logical requirements of the definition of the concept, nevertheless they make it possible to evaluate human happiness, especially those signs that are necessary to achieve happiness. According to one of these approaches (Balashov, 2008) in order to be happy, a person must have physical health and material wealth and all this must be enveloped in love and creativity (a mixture of happiness). In the mixture of happiness, we also include positive guidelines for life and give the following formula for happiness in table 1 (Mikaelian, 2011).

The material side of happiness		The spiritual side of happiness		Blend of happiness
Physical health	Material and social wealth	Spiritual health	Spiritual wealth	Positive guidelines for life, creativity

Table 1: The formula of happiness

How much does mathematical education contribute to human happiness? Is the child happy in the mathematical class at school? Paul Ernst (2018) rightly believes that most of these children are unhappy. Moreover, for students who are not interested in mathematics, a mathematics lesson turns into a place of imprisonment (Mikaelian, 2011). How does the process of teaching mathematics affect the formation of each component of happiness? A. Schopenhauer finds that nine-tenths of human happiness depends on physical health (Schopenhauer, 1990). Mathematical education contributes to the acquisition of material wealth and in terms of acquiring social wealth, it can have a double meaning: it plays a positive role in cooperative relationships and even plays a negative role in family, friendship and similar relationships (Mikaelian, 2011). On the formation of mental health, as a component of moral purity, mathematical education can have both a positive and a negative impact (Mikaelian, 2011; Ernest, 2018). As for mental wealth, mathematical education has only a positive impact. It contributes to the formation and development of intelligence, thinking, imagination, attention, memory and volitional qualities. It also plays an important role in the formation of various aesthetic values (Mikaelian, 2015b, 2019).

Mathematics education can have a double meaning in shaping a blend of happiness. The influence on the formation of optimism and faith is mostly positive, and on the formation of love of life, cheerfulness and a cheerful mood it is mostly negative. For students who are able to grasp mathematical material, that is the patterns in it and their beauty, mathematics is an inexhaustible source of love and hope, while for students deprived of such abilities, it brings only hatred and torment (Mikaelian, 2011; Ernest, 2018). The same picture applies to creativity.

The possibilities are similar to those of physical education at school. Only these two school subjects provide students with inexhaustible opportunities for creativity and unfortunately restricted to some students (Mikaelian, 2011).

The meaning of life is usually associated with the problem of setting goals and their implementation. Two main goals are associated with the problems of self-preserving and preserving the human species. The first problem is solved through professional activity, while the second – through the creation of family. In the former mathematical education plays a positive role, but in the latter its role can be negative (Mikaelian, 2011).

The problem of formation of moral values in the context of modern approaches to mathematical education

One of the modern approaches to the development of mathematics education is its *humanization*: humanistic approach in the process of teaching mathematics. One of the ways to implement this approach, together with the knowledge of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world, is the formation of values and value orientations of students. In the diversity of values, the most important place is occupied by moral values that for the most part become the cause of value orientations and determine human behaviour. As noted, the process of teaching mathematics has great potential for the formation of moral values, the identification of which becomes one of the ways to humanize mathematics education (Mikaelian & Yenokyan, 2016).

In the works (Mikaelian, 2020b; Yenokyan, 2020) the problem of formation of moral values in the context of *informatization* of mathematical education is considered. In particular, the formation of the values of tolerance and fairness in the conditions of informatization of mathematical education is considered. The authors propose specific ways of solving the problem.

One of the modern trends in the development of mathematical education is *historicization*: inclusion of individual episodes of history in the process of teaching mathematics, which can also be successfully applied in the formation of moral values. In (Yenokyan, 2015) the question of the formation of moral values through teaching mathematical problems in the Armenian educational environment of the 7th-19th centuries is considered. It is shown that in the mentioned period and especially in the 7th century, the Armenian mathematician Anania Shirakatsi and other authors created mathematical problems in which situations with moral content are widespread, which contribute to the formation of moral values.

It is extremely difficult to turn the issue of the formation of values, moral values in particular, into the goal of a specific educational process, since it is not valued as knowledge or as a skill and is not controlled. Its implementation is due to the professional and moral approaches of the teacher. However, even if desired, the mathematics teacher is not able to implement it, since textbooks and methodological literature do not aimed at the goal. To solve the problem, we propose to apply value-oriented mathematics teaching (Mikaelian,

2018a,b; Yenokyan, 2018b). Together with the formation of knowledge, a value-oriented approach becomes the goal of lessons and the task of value-formation. In (Mikaelian & Mkrtchyan, (2020), the effectiveness of the use of elements of logic in the organization of value-oriented teaching is shown, and in (Mkrtchyan & Yenokyan 2016) a value-oriented approach is applied in the process of learning the elements of logic. In (Yenokyan, 2018a) a value-oriented approach is applied in high school in organizing function learning.

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